

The Intimate Virtuoso: Embodied Technique and Aesthetic Innovation in Maria Szymanowska's *Études and Preludes*

Hongbo Cai

Music Division, The Juilliard School, USA

Received: Sep 14, 2025

Accepted: Oct 15, 2025

Published: Oct 24, 2025

Abstract— The article explores "feminine virtuosity" through the lens of Maria Szymanowska's *Études and Preludes* (1820), positioning Szymanowska within the historical evolution of études. It argues that her work redefines pianistic virtuosity by emphasizing flexibility, multidimensionality, and expressive depth over power and clarity, shaped by her identity as a female musician in salon culture. Through score analysis, historical research, and performance-based interviews on a Conrad Graf fortepiano, the study highlights her ergonomic innovations. By restoring Szymanowska's place in music history, the article challenges exclusionary canons and reconsiders the role of gender and embodiment in shaping pianistic literature.

Keywords— Maria Szymanowska, feminine virtuosity, études, piano literature, gender and music, 19th-Century Music

I. THE BODY AT THE KEYBOARD

To this day, études are still largely perceived as functional exercises for physical skill development, with the primary metric being the perfection of evenness and sound quality. Études are often viewed as preparatory training for more complex and mature pieces and as the benchmark of virtuosity. Despite the rich contributions of concert études from Romantic composers, the étude genre still struggles to gain its integrity, largely overshadowed by the mechanical, stereotypical image established by Czerny and Clementi in piano pedagogy. Yet as early as 1820, Polish pianist and composer Maria Szymanowska offered an alternative conception of virtuosity through her *Twenty Études and Preludes*. Her work represents a revolutionary contribution to the étude genre by transcending the mechanical, pedagogical exercises typical of her contemporaries and pioneering an intimate, layered form of pianistic virtuosity shaped by her identity as a female composer. By utilizing the qualities of salon music and creatively incorporating ergonomic factors—like joint mobility—into her compositional process, Szymanowska not only increased the piano's sonic potential but also hinted at aspects of Chopin and Liszt's Romantic piano literature. However, because of the gendered biases of 19th-century musical institutions, which disregarded non-linear, multidimensional forms of musical expression as being incompatible with conventional ideas of "greatness" and excluded female creative voices, her achievements have generally remained unrecognized. By presenting Szymanowska as a revolutionary whose approach to composition and performance—marked by flexibility, lightness, and multi-dimensionality—offers a radical rethinking of what constitutes feminine virtuosity, this thesis seeks to restore her rightful place in the history of piano études.

In attempting to complete this research, the initial challenge lies in constructing performance practices without the support of recordings or video documentation. While traditional methodologies such as score analysis and historical research provide a foundation, a more immersive approach for this study involves approaching existing pieces from the performer's bodily perspective. As Le Guin states in [1], "Because the performer's relationship to the work of art must have an extensively explored bodily element, a performing identification with a composer is based on a particular type of knowledge which could be called carnal." The methodology introduced by Le Guin is fundamental in making this study possible. Building on this, two additional complex issues arise: we must consider variables such as gender and instrument constraints. Wagner's ergonomic study in [2] reveals significant biological differences between male and female hands, including finger span and joint flexibility. As a female composer, Szymanowska may have utilized her physical advantages to mitigate her physical limitations. Moreover, the modern

piano is not the instrument for which Szymanowska composed; it would be unjust to make assumptions about her techniques and intentions based on the dimensions and soundscape of the modern piano. As a result, I proposed to the Historical Performance Department at The Juilliard School to use their 6.5-octave fortepiano made by Conrad Graf as a reference instrument. Additionally, a sight-reading session was conducted with two female pianists from Juilliard to document their instinctual responses to play certain techniques based on their physical intuition. This study gratefully acknowledges the consent of these two pianists and the support of the Historical Performance Department for granting access to the instrument.

II. HISTORIOGRAPHY: CRAMER AND CLEMENTI

Historically speaking, Szymanowska is often regarded as the first composer to introduce the *étude* genre to Poland. However, in contrast to traditional views, a more radical yet not unfounded argument might be that it was precisely Szymanowska who catalyzed the transformation of the *étude* genre—from mechanical and pedagogical exercises to a refined and virtuosic display of technical prowess—considering the period in which her works were composed. Her *Twenty Études and Preludes*, written in 1819, situates itself interestingly in the timeline of piano *étude* literature: it predates Moscheles' *24 Études*, Op. 70 (published in 1825-26) by more than five years, Hummel's *Études*, Op. 125 (published in 1834) by fourteen years, Czerny's *The School of Velocity*, Op. 299 (published in 1833) by over a decade, and Chopin's landmark *Études*, Op. 10 (first published in 1833, with some written as early as 1829) by approximately ten years. Compared to later developments, the conventions of piano *études* available to Szymanowska before and during her time were relatively scarce. These included Cramer's *84 Études*, Op. 30 & 40 (completed in 1804 and 1807-1808), Clementi's *Preludes and Exercises*, Op. 43 (published in 1811), and a subsequent work *Gradus ad Parnassum*, Op. 44 (published in three books in 1817, 1819, and 1836).

Fig. 1 Passages from Clementi's *Gradus ad Parnassum*, Op. 44, demonstrating passagework focused on finger independence and scalar repetition. C.F. Peters edition, n.d.[1868], plate nos. 4649/4651.

Cramer's *études* and Clementi's exercises are often compared as foundational training materials for aspiring professional pianists. In the preface to the Schirmer publication of *Fifty Selected Piano Studies by Cramer*, Hans von Bülow wrote: "Cramer's pianoforte-studies, as a cultural means for the pianist's execution and delivery, a means not only unexcelled but also—with the exception of Muzio Clementi's *Gradus ad Parnassum*—one as yet but approximately equaled by any other collection of studies...their well-considered and methodic employment must have the gain of...an already comparatively developed degree of mechanical and intellectual ripeness on the part of the player." Written in 1868, Bülow's assessment precisely situates Cramer and Clementi's reception and position within piano training: they were viewed as practical, fundamental teaching materials designed to train the solidity of basic finger technique. With extensive references to metronomic markings and musical signs, Bülow makes little mention of Cramer's musical achievements, nor does he discuss whether these *études* expanded the vocabulary of piano technique. On the contrary, Bülow even emphasizes that the remarkable effectiveness

of Cramer's études comes from their homogeneity and repetitiveness. He highlighted in [3] "Sensations of that which is homogeneous... Precisely in connection with the necessity of acquiring by perseverance any special kind of mechanical expertness, the charm of a certain variety in homogeneity tends to refresh and stimulate."

In the sense of achieving a remarkable impression through repetition, Cramer can indeed be seen as the precursor to Clementi's exercises. According to [4], in two of his consecutive letters to his father after listening to Clementi's performance, Mozart in 1783 wrote that "Clementi plays well... His greatest strength lies in his passages in thirds. Apart from this, he has not a kreutzer's worth of taste or feeling, in short he is simply a mechanicus." As Plantinga points out in the same article, Clementi's *Gradus ad Parnassum* was an object of parody in Debussy's *Children's Corner Suite*, which "meant to recall the agreeable tedium of the child-pianist's keyboard exercises... *Gradus ad Parnassum* by Muzio Clementi." Clementi's études have left a certain stereotype in music history, one that reflects what pianists before 1820 generally associated with études. Despite numerous attempts by existing scholarship to conduct a thorough reappraisal of Clementi's oeuvre, the purpose of this work is to remain within the confines of his études. From a textual and aural perspective, the stigma of repetition and the sheer display of finger dexterity and strength are evident in Clementi's études. In *Preludes and Exercises, Op. 43*, the practice of scalar movement pervades the entire set, whereas in *Gradus ad Parnassum* there is some improvement, as each short piece focuses on a different technical aspect. However, as Figure 1 shows, these techniques were designed primarily for finger improvement, with little intention of being performed in concert settings, and were often achieved at the cost of textural beauty and auditory refinement.

III. BEYOND MECHANICS: SZYMANOWSKA'S INNOVATION

Given the context of its creation, and especially considering the prevailing stereotypes about the étude genre of the time, Szymanowska's vision of the potential scope of études is beyond astonishing. It can be said that she not only transcended her era but also foreshadowed the emergence of the next. The numerous innovations in texture invite listeners to compare her work more with Chopin than with her contemporaries, such as Hummel and Moscheles. For instance, No. 12, praised by Dobrzański in [5], evokes Chopin's Étude Op. 25, No. 4 with its continuous leaping texture in both hands, as shown in Figure 2a and Figure 2b. The difference lies in Chopin's refinement of her texture, leaving the downbeat empty and placing the melodic notes on the offbeat. Coincidentally, just as Chopin enters the leaping texture from a suspension on an offbeat, Szymanowska similarly suspends the harmony of the first measure on a dominant seventh chord of D in E-flat major, using a deceptive cadence to lead into E-flat major.

Fig. 2a Opening measures of Szymanowska Étude No. 12, illustrating leaping textures in both hands and harmonic suspension. PWM Edition, 2022.

The harmonic suspension here is arguably even more remarkable than Chopin's. As the deceptive cadence is not definitive, the shadow of the D dominant seventh continuously suggests a risk of slipping back to G major/minor. Moreover, Szymanowska adds a B-flat to the suspension of the dominant chord, creating a dissonance of a minor second and augmented fifth, making this harmony an overtly romantic color ahead of its time in the 1820s. From both an acoustic and textural perspective, No. 12 demonstrates that Szymanowska conceived of the étude not merely as an exercise in finger dexterity, but as an exploration of pianistic technique and its potential tonal possibilities. Therefore, it serves not only as a challenge to the physical boundaries of the pianist, but also as a challenge to the boundaries of the

instrument itself—a revolutionary way of thinking that can be found only in the études of masters such as Chopin, Liszt, and Debussy..

Fig. 2b Excerpt from Chopin *Étude in A minor, Op. 25, No. 4*, demonstrating refined offbeat leaping textures and melodic displacement. National Edition, edited by Jan Ekier and Paweł Kamiński.

Another étude worth mentioning is No. 3, where the innovative texture and technical difficulty once again surpass mere displays of agility and strength, reminding us of the more subtle dynamic conversation between hands and registers illustrated in Chopin's études. As shown in Figure 3a, the primary technical challenge here does not come from the obvious rapid right-hand passages, but rather from balancing the upper and lower voices in the right hand, while maintaining the necessary evenness and clarity in the fast passages, to highlight the notes that fall on the downbeat. Played predominantly by the index finger and thumb, these notes should be connected to form a smoothly phrased melody. Interestingly, Szymanowska places significant emphasis on the second beat, creating an off-beat accent that, when executed well, results in a lighter, more dance-like sense of rotation. The rhythmic pattern in the left-hand makes this even more intricate: the downbeat is a single note, while the two weak beats are octaves. The natural tendency might lead the pianist to emphasize the latter two beats, but since the emphasis in the right hand is already on the second beat, the left hand must maintain the natural hierarchy of the triple meter. Otherwise, the performance risks falling into rhythmic dislocation.

We find a similar but more complex rhythmic interplay in Chopin's *Étude, Op. 10, No. 10*: as seen in Figure 3b, the left hand plays in groups of three while the right hand plays in groups of two, with special emphasis on the second and fifth groups within a 12/8 bar. However, the accent is not on the downbeat of the two-note group but rather on the downbeat of the three-note group. In this sense, there is a rhythmic overlap and lock-in point between the hands. Such an intricate mechanism of beat and register is a profound exploration into piano writing itself rather than a pursuit of technical display. On this level, we again see Szymanowska as a musical precursor to Chopin's rhythmic experiments.

Fig. 3a Excerpt from Szymanowska *Étude No. 3*, illustrating off-beat melodic emphasis, inner-hand voicing, and rotational articulation. PWM Edition.

Fig. 3b Measures of Chopin Étude in A-flat major, Op. 10, No. 10, showing crossrhythmic interaction between duple and triple groupings. National Edition.

IV. PIANISTIC BODY

Among Szymanowska's études, another piece warrants particular attention due to its specific technical demands and additional requirements concerning hand size, offering us insights into her definition of virtuosity. The C major Étude, Op. 6, exhibits an exceptionally demanding technique for both the left and right hands: as shown in Figure 4, the lower voices maintain repeated double notes, while the upper voice performs ascending scales. Each occurrence of this figuration necessitates a span of a tenth within a single hand. Although most male pianists on modern pianos possess the ability to span a tenth, Szymanowska complicates this by having the index finger and thumb form a third interval, while requiring the little finger to span an octave simultaneously. Such a reach is nearly unimaginable on a modern piano.

Fig. 4 Excerpt from Szymanowska Étude in C major, No. 6, demonstrating simultaneous wide-span voicing and double-note figuration within a single hand. PWM Edition.

According to an example of a technical report in [6], the octave width on a modern piano is approximately 164–165 millimeters, which implies an average white key width of about 23.5 millimeters. In contrast, the 6.5-octave Conrad Graf fortepiano—serving as a reference for pianos of Szymanowska's era—features an average white key width of 22 millimeters, resulting in an octave span of roughly 154 millimeters, according to examinations in [7]. Even with a nearly one-centimeter reduction in keyboard spacing, performing Étude No. 6 on a fortepiano from Szymanowska's time remains highly challenging. It can be argued that the difficulty lies not in the keyboard's width but in her compositional technique, which requires the separation of the index and little fingers by an octave while maintaining the thumb in a downward third. However, we should realize that this arrangement is virtually impossible to execute simultaneously, even for male performers on a fortepiano.

Sources from Dobrzański, an award-winning scholar on Szymanowska, state in [8] that "some of the chords are extremely challenging or simply impossible to execute (particularly in No. 6), indicating that the composer had at her disposal unusually large hands. It would appear that having large hands did not affect Szymanowska's impressive finger dexterity." Dobrzański's conclusions regarding Szymanowska's hand dimensions, derived solely from her compositional techniques, may be sufficient but not necessary. Historical records do not provide additional evidence to corroborate the assertion that Szymanowska possessed hands capable of effortlessly executing such spans. The questions worth asking here might be: What if Szymanowska did not intend this merely as an exercise in unison for finger stretching? Might

there be additional technical effects that she envisioned for both the performer and herself in this étude? Modern recordings of this piece by Khouri, Ciborowska, and Dobrzański render the passage with the left and right hands aligned in unison. However, a meticulous examination of the third measure reveals that these performers achieve the intended effect by omitting the C note that the thumb is originally supposed to play.

Figure 5. Excerpt from Chopin Étude in E major, Op. 10, No. 11, illustrating arpeggiated textures and harp-like sound effects. National Edition.

A plausible interpretation is that, after exceeding a certain span, Szymanowska employs arpeggiation rather than unison, similar to the technique utilized by Chopin in Étude, Op. 10, No. 11. Notably, the primary technical challenge of Étude, Op. 10, No. 11 lies in creating harp-like sound effects, wherein the lower voices maintain static intervals while the upper voices predominantly move in a stepwise motion, as shown in Figure 5. Additional evidence supporting this point is that Szymanowska marked the tempo of the étude as "moderato," while the "marcato" marking signifies the prominence of the melodic line. Even when progressing in sixteenth notes, there remains ample time to execute the arpeggios smoothly. Considering the affinity between Szymanowska's études and Chopin's compositions, and acknowledging that Chopin indeed attended Szymanowska's farewell concert in Warsaw on January 15, 1826, according to letters in [9], by which time Szymanowska's études had been completed five to six years earlier, it is arguable that certain techniques developed by Szymanowska may have influenced Chopin's compositional practices. Specifically, Szymanowska's innovative approaches to handling expansive hand spans and her integration of arpeggiated textures as a full-ranged harp in No. 6 could have provided Chopin with novel technical and expressive pianistic auralities. In Chopin's private teaching, the flexibility of wrist movement was repeatedly emphasized. In describing Chopin's finger technique, Eigeldinger notes in [10] that "(Chopin) sometimes lies as though dead at the wrist, but keeps always a living, active link from each finger to the hand.... When the wrist is not passive, the sensorial power runs through the whole hand right through to the fingers, paralyzing them." Here, the wrist serves as the connection between the hand and the fingers, using wrist movement to drive the fingers, thereby making the technique appear effortless on the fingers themselves. This approach is precisely what is required when performing large-span arpeggios.

Fig. 6 Measures of Szymanowska Étude No. 11, featuring rapid, wide leaps suggestive of early wrist technique. PWM Edition.

Further instances displayed by later études also support the possibility of Szymanowska's use of the wrist technique at a proficient level, an example of which is Étude No. 11 shown in Figure 6. In this étude, the huge leaps from both the left and right hands easily remind us of *La Campanella* by Liszt and its imitation of crossing strings on violins. However, from a performance practice standpoint, achieving such consecutive leaps with its extreme reach of a sixteenth is impractical without the dexterity of smooth wrist

movement. The fact that Szymanowska composes in such a way proves the technique to be in her skill set. The wrist enables fingers to reach beyond their normal extent, and the finger remains passive, carrying weight as it travels; this is the identical technique used to play arpeggiated large chords. Therefore, from the perspective of piano pedagogy, Szymanowska may have pioneered the use of the wrist in her études, relying less on finger extension or arm movement to achieve large-span effects.

Moreover, Swartz's writings from [9] corroborate Szymanowska's affinity for arpeggiated figuration. This not only represents a continuation of the techniques she inherited from her teacher, John Field, but also aligns with the typical context of her performances, specifically salon music characterized by its lightness and charm. According to Swartz's study, "we find melodic figurations typical of those melodies found in much of the salon music of the early nineteenth century. Such musical characteristics include ... the delicate, light, arpeggiated, 'filigree' writing favored by Field and other salon composers such as Hummel and Lessel." In contrast to modern recordings that render this passage as march-like chord repetitions to flaunt additional hand spans, a more historically accurate portrayal involves a slower, elegant performance characterized by wrist-driven playing. This approach distinctly separates the lower accompaniment from the upper melody, showcasing the piano's ability to emulate the harp across different registers, thereby more faithfully reflecting historical descriptions of Szymanowska's performance style. From this, it becomes evident that Szymanowska's innovative understanding of virtuosity in her études originated from salon music, as well as the significant insights this might have offered Chopin regarding physical technique, piano timbre, and musical temperament.

Study on the principles of carnal musicology further established the performance techniques that Szymanowska may have employed in her études. Among other études, No. 7 received particular attention due to its unusually awkward leaps in the left hand, illustrated in Figure 7. In this piece, the left-hand figuration often features a bass ornament an octave below the primary note, and after playing the primary note, the left hand frequently needs to twist upward by as much as an eleventh to reach the next two notes. Extensive discussion and numerous tryouts take place as to how potentially this effect might be achieved and what sonority Szymanowska might be envisioning. Under the marking "scherzando" with a meter of 6/8, the music has to be light with the arpeggiated notes granular but translucent, a "filigree" writing style once more. Firstly, the full charm of this passage can only be realized on the fortepiano, the instrument for which Szymanowska most likely wrote. On a modern piano, with its powerful bass tone, the left-hand part tends to sound too thick and heavy, overshadowing the right-hand melody. Furthermore, on a modern piano, the sound does not decay immediately; instead, it typically swells before beginning to decay, especially when using the pedal. Additionally, Szymanowska often specifically marked an accent on the second eighth note of the left hand in 6/8 time, which, as indicated in the score, is challenging to achieve on a modern piano without sounding clumsy. This effect is only attainable on the fortepiano, where the perceptible strike has a timbre more akin to that of a xylophone.

Fig. 7 Ending sections of Szymanowska Étude No. 7, showcasing wide left-hand leaps and ornamental bass figures. PWM Edition.

In performance practice, there are two approaches to executing this technique. The first method involves using the thumb as a pivot; the wrist rotates upward until the index finger reaches the next key, completing the shift in balance. The second method relies on a rapid shift in hand position, with minimal movement of the thumb, covering the distance and landing the weight directly on the index finger. The fundamental difference between the two methods lies in the focus on balance: in the first approach, the weight remains

on the keys throughout, whereas in the second, the balance leaves the keys during the leap, requiring more wrist flexibility. Interestingly, in the context of piano exercises before the advanced level, playing techniques that involve leaving the keys are generally not recommended. As a more challenging approach, it requires the fingers to have a heightened sense of touch while the wrist must maintain both flexibility and support simultaneously.

On the fortepiano, given that the keys are significantly lighter than those on a modern piano, it is easy for the performer to unintentionally strike unwanted notes during the rotational movement. Additionally, as previously mentioned, the fortepiano has a quicker decay time, necessitating more complete preparation before pressing the key and a clear articulation at the exact moment of the key being pressed down. The first approach may provide greater accuracy when the upward-turning finger reaches the intended note; however, due to the shift in balance, it cannot ensure that force is delivered precisely to the fingertip at the moment of contact, risking a muted sound and an unsmooth transition. Furthermore, while the bass register below a certain range on a modern piano is more about producing a resonant sound than articulating an exact pitch, the fortepiano is quite the opposite. Each touch on the fortepiano yields a distinct pitch, a result of its lighter sound. In this sense, due to the characteristics of the instrument, Szymanowska likely employed the second technique—particularly considering the exceptionally low bass line in the penultimate measure. This technique is riskier, lighter, but allows for greater control over articulation and tone, ensuring that each note is executed with clarity and forms an integral part of effective phrasing.

This playing technique also aligns with our understanding of the physiological structure of the female hand. In Wagner's thorough anthropometric study on pianists' hands in [2], the author states that although men generally have a greater finger span than women, "In all the characteristics of passive mobility, significantly higher values were shown for the women; so, too, with the exception of the spread 3-5 in women, there were significantly higher values throughout for the left hand." Wagner further suggests that this increased mobility compensates for the smaller hand size of female pianists, enabling them to achieve a similar finger span. Passive joint mobility is precisely the technique required to play large-span arpeggio figurations, as discussed throughout the examples in this article. Based on this, in *Étude No. 7*, the second proposed technique also aligns better with women's aptitude for passive mobility, as it relies on the wrist's flexibility to reposition and press down on new keys after leaving the keyboard. In contrast, the first method emphasizes the stretching of the fingers themselves. During a sight-reading session of *No. 7* on a 6.5-octave Graf fortepiano, two female pianists from Juilliard also confirmed the necessity of this practice to execute the paragraph for feminine hands of average sizes. For female pianists, executing the second method is inherently more natural and easier to control compared to the first. Due to their smaller wrists, they can more easily shift to new positions, and for the same reason, they do not need to be overly concerned with the weight of key depression. Conversely, using the first method requires additional practice, as the extra finger stretching often results in a loss of control, leading to unintended heavy accents and making it difficult to maintain the ideal continuity of broken chords. In this sense, Szymanowska's compositional approach once again reveals a uniquely feminine form of virtuosity. This technique utilizes wrist flexibility to lift off the keys and shift gravity focus, which proves more challenging for men, who often rely on the advantage of larger hand sizes. This also explains why exercises focusing on wrist flexibility are almost absent in the *études* of Clementi and Cramer.

However, the concept of "feminine virtuosity" cannot be understood as an inherent tendency collectively unique to women, since the relationship between the performer and pianistic technique is often highly individualized. As the author acknowledges, there exists considerable diversity of hand types among women, making it impossible to generalize these characteristics under a single defining trait. More precisely, "feminine virtuosity" should be understood as a musical and technical aesthetic that diversifies and reconfigures the traditional notion of virtuosity, rather than opposing it. Its emergence was facilitated by the salon culture largely shaped by women, as well as by certain physical attributes possessed by some female performers that contributed to distinctive technical approaches.

Thus, the concept of *feminine virtuosity* does not denote an isolated or categorically distinct idea of virtuosity; rather, it acknowledges the contribution of the female body and collective female agency to our modern understanding of virtuosity. It seeks to deconstruct the ostensibly solid notion of virtuosity by revealing the elements within it that derive from women's embodied experience and their historical participation in its formation.

V. THE SALON EFFECT

In the above details, we recognize that Szymanowska's compositional logic for études and ideas for virtuosity differs significantly from that of her contemporaries. Rather than showcasing power and clarity, her études represent a simultaneous demonstration of both the sonority of the piano and the maturity of musicianship. Unlike exercises intended to prepare the performer for more substantial works, her études were more akin to ready-made concert pieces, foreshadowing those of Liszt. This notion is also affirmed in the introduction of the new PWM edition of Szymanowska's études: "Szymanowska's études should not be assigned solely to the type of the etude-exercise, but also to the second group...representing études de perfectionnement, they are also sometimes linked to the category of the étude de salon, and also, in a sense, the étude de concert. Szymanowska may have preluded in concerts and performed her études in the salon." This statement directs us to the environment that nurtured such a compositional and acoustic style—Szymanowska's salon.

Szymanowska's compositions were quintessentially salon music—light, ornate, and suited to intimate gatherings rather than grand concert performances. Her works, including mazurkas, études, nocturnes, and polonaises, often embodied characteristics such as "filigree" melodic writing, which was delicate and highly ornamented, a way of showcasing virtuosity unique to her setting and personality. However, this does not imply that the seriousness of Szymanowska's works is diminished because of the private and lighthearted nature of their performance settings. On the contrary, as demonstrated in the previous score analysis, the prominent status of salons in the early nineteenth century ensured that the music performed in these settings possessed a high level of artistic quality. As Swartz further illustrates, "Salon music was considered elegant, refined, and attractive early in the nineteenth century, but later in the century the composition of salon pieces was carried out by amateurs, dilettantes, and commercial composers who merely furnished pieces for mass consumption." Furthermore, Szymanowska's salons were not merely gatherings for musical performance; they were significant cultural events that fostered intellectual and artistic exchange. Swartz testifies, "Her home in St. Petersburg became a cultural haven for artists, writers, and composers visiting and living there." Among figures such as Adam Mickiewicz, Alexander Pushkin, and Michael Glinka, it is not difficult to see why Szymanowska's études possessed a certain experimental quality regarding piano writing and tonal possibilities. The lightness of the salon setting may have fostered and encouraged her innovative explorations.

Similarly, Szymanowska is not the only composer whose work has been understated due to the context and aesthetics exclusive to salon music, which differ from the traditionally defined settings of formal concerts. In her study of Madame Brillon, Cypess in [11] also highlights these often-overlooked musical qualities: "She (M. Brillon) apparently did not concern herself with conventions of voice leading and counterpoint. Instead, she prioritized more ephemeral aspects of music, such as timbre and texture. I consider her musicianship and her salon as a whole, in terms of the ephemeral experiences that she valued... in qualities of music that cannot be captured in notation: special effects of timbre, the blurred sounds caused by damper-raising pedals." Here, Cypess draws an incisive parallel within salon music, confirming the shared qualities of music produced in women-led salons. Holding the same ephemeral nature and intimate atmosphere in common, we are compelled to move beyond musical notation's limitations to decipher Szymanowska's music and boldly imagine the sonic effects she envisioned. For this reason, the concept of virtuosity as a display of strength or homogeneity is not particularly applicable to her études. Instead, we should seek meaning in more subtle parameters such as polyphony, texture, and timbre.

VI. FEMININE VIRTUOSITY

In her études, Szymanowska not only showcases mature musicianship both as composer and performer but also raises an innovative concept on the idea of virtuosity itself for the genre of étude, however, music history has not acknowledged her contribution to its due extent as a result of the gender stereotypes. In her bold thesis, Citron argues that women's ways of perceiving and approaching music are fundamentally different. The apparent absence of female composers within the established canon is not solely due to social or technical exclusion but also stems from a different, embodied, non-linear, and multilayered mode of thinking. This "female thought pattern" as discussed in [12] by Citron has no place in a system defined by male standards. If we consider this system an "institution of power," women like Szymanowska were

excluded from the canon, positioned as guerrilla-like figures practicing a marginalized form of musical expression, simply because they could not be incorporated into the power structure. As a result, each woman had to build her career from scratch. Even though Szymanowska successfully established herself as a female virtuoso and salon organizer, her musical achievements were still not fully recognized within the ranks of established composers.

Even on her time, the same social and ideological constraints also affected Szymanowska. As a brewer's daughter, a performer constantly on tour, and a divorced woman raising three children, she was easily subjected to social stigma. This was compounded by the music world's established notion that equated the image of a great composer with being male, thereby reinforcing negative conclusions about women. Trochimczyk in [13] concluded in her study on Szymanowska's professional image, "the Polish pianist was surrounded with prejudice of this kind from the time of her youth. Negative statements about women's lack of compositional ability connected to their weak intellectual capabilities appeared in writings." However, the "female thought patterns" discussed by Citron offer a unique perspective for examining the existing literature by women composers, particularly in terms of composition and performance style. Szymanowska's études exemplify this multidimensional and layered approach. Her compositions extend beyond mere demonstrations of form and technique, focusing instead on the exploration and expression of pianistic writing and sonority. The intimate and elegant salon quality of her works represents a form of virtuosity that had yet to be fully recognized and valued within the male-dominated musical canon—a virtuosity of flexibility, lightness, and multidimensionality. These distinct qualities are ones that would later be appreciated when they were prominent in Chopin but unfortunately missed their due when displayed by the "eternally feminine."

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